

Convertible Bond Risk Framework

Tim Xiao

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a framework for calculating fair value and risk of convertible bonds. A typical convertible bond arbitrage employs delta-neutral hedging, in which an arbitrageur buys a convertible bond and sells the underlying equity at the current delta. Delta neutral hedging not only removes small directional risks but also is capable of making a profit on an explosive upside or downside breakout if the position's gamma is kept positive. As such, delta neutral hedging is great for uncertain stocks that are expected to make huge breakouts in either direction. Since convertible bonds are issued mainly by start-up or small companies, the chance of a large movement in either direction is very likely. Even for very small movements in the underlying stock price, profits can still be generated from the yield of the convertible bond and the interest rebate for the short position.

Key Words: hybrid financial instrument, convertible bond, convertible underpricing, convertible arbitrage, default time approach, default probability approach, jump diffusion.

1. Introduction

There is a rich literature on the subject of convertible bonds. Arguably, the first widely adopted model among practitioners is the one presented by Goldman Sachs (1994) and then formalized by Tsiveriotis and Fernandes (1998). The Goldman Sachs' solution is a simple one factor model with an equity binomial tree to value convertible bonds. The model considers the probability of conversion at every node. If the convertible is certain to remain a bond, it is then discounted by a risky discount rate that reflects the credit risk of the issuer. If the convertible is certain to be converted, it is then discounted by the risk-free interest rate that is equivalent to default free.

Grimwood and Hodges (2002) indicate that the Goldman Sachs model is incoherent because it assumes that bonds are susceptible to credit risk but equities are not. Ayache *et al* (2003) conclude that the Tsiveriotis-Fernandes model is inherently unsatisfactory due to its unrealistic assumption of stock prices being unaffected by bankruptcy. To correct this weakness, Davis and Lischka (1999), Andersen and Buffum (2004), Bloomberg (2009), and Carr and Linetsky (2006) etc., propose a jump-diffusion model to explore defaultable stock price dynamics. They all believe that under a risk-neutral measure the expected rate of return on a defaultable stock must be equal to the risk-free interest rate. The jump-diffusion model characterizes the default time/jump directly.

Although we agree that under a risk-neutral measure the market price of risk and risk preferences are irrelevant to asset pricing (Hull, 2003) and thereby the expectation of a risk-free¹ asset grows at the risk-free interest rate, we are not convinced that the expected rate of return on a defaultable asset must be also equal to the risk-free rate. We argue that unlike market risk, credit risk actually has a significant impact on asset prices. This is why regulators, such as International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS), etc. require financial institutions to report a credit value adjustment (CVA) in addition to the risk-free mark-to-market (MTM) value to reflect credit risk (Xiao,

¹ Here, *risk-free* means free of credit risk, but not necessarily of market risk

2013). By definition, a CVA is the difference between the risk-free value and the risky value of an asset/portfolio subject to credit risk. CVA implies that the risk-free value should not be equal to the risky value in the presence of default risk. As a matter of fact, we will prove that the expected return of a defaultable asset under a risk-neutral measure actually grows at a risky rate rather than the risk-free rate. This conclusion is very important for risky valuation.

This article makes a theoretical and empirical contribution to the study of convertible bonds. In contrast to the above mentioned literature, we present a model that is based on the probability distribution (or intensity) of a default jump (or a default time) rather than the default jump itself, as the default jump is usually inaccessible (see Duffie and Huang (1996), Jarrow and Protter (2004), etc).

Valuation under our risky model can be solved by common numerical methods, such as, Monte Carlo simulation, tree/lattice approaches, or partial differential equation (PDE) solutions. The PDE algorithm is elaborated in this paper, but of course the methodology can be easily extended to tree/lattice or Monte Carlo.

The most important parameter to be determined is the volatility input for valuation. A common approach in the market is to use the at-the-money (ATM) implied Black-Scholes volatility to price convertible bonds. However, most liquid stock options have relatively short maturates (rarely more than 8 years). As a result, some authors, such as Ammann *et al* (2003), Loncarski *et al* (2009), Zabolotnyuk *et al* (2010), have to make do with historical volatilities. Therefore, we segment the sample into two sets according to maturity: a short-maturity class (0 ~ 8 years) and a long-maturity class (> 8 years). For the short-maturity class, we use the ATM implied Black-Scholes volatility for valuation, whereas for the long-maturity class, we calculate the historical volatility as the annualized standard deviation of the daily log returns of the last 2 years and then price the convertible bond based on this real-world volatility.

It is useful to examine the basics of the convertible arbitrage strategy. A typical convertible bond arbitrage employs delta-neutral hedging, in which an arbitrageur buys a convertible bond and sells the underlying equity at the current delta (see Choi *et al* (2009), Loncarski *et al* (2009), etc.). With delta neutral positions, the sign of Gamma is important. If Gamma is negative, the portfolio profits so long as the

underlying equity remains stable. If Gamma is positive, the portfolio will profit from large movements in the stock price in either direction (Somanath, 2011).

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: The model is presented in Section 2. Section 3 elaborates the PDE approach; Section 4 discusses the empirical results. The conclusions are provided in Section 5. Some numerical implementation details are contained in the appendices.

2 Model

From a practitioner's perspective, Monte Carlo is a "last resort" and "least preferred" method, whereas lattice or PDE approaches suffer from the curse of dimensionality: The number of evaluations and computational cost increase exponentially with the dimension of the problem, making it impractical to use in more than two dimensions.

We consider a filtered probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{P})$ satisfying the usual conditions, where Ω denotes a sample space, \mathcal{F} denotes a σ -algebra, \mathcal{P} denotes a probability measure, and $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ denotes a filtration.

The risk-free stock price process can be described as

$$dS(t) = r(t)S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) \quad (1)$$

where $S(t)$ denotes the stock price, $r(t)$ denotes the risk-free interest rate, σ denotes the volatility, $W(t)$ denotes a Wiener process.

The expectation of equation (1) is

$$E(dS(t)|\mathcal{F}_t) = r(t)S(t)dt \quad (2)$$

where $E(\bullet|\mathcal{F}_t)$ is the expectation conditional on the \mathcal{F}_t .

Equation (2) tells us that in a risk-neutral world, the expected return on a risk-free stock is the risk-free interest rate $r(t)$, i.e., the discounted stock price under the risk neutral measure is a martingale process.

Next, we turn to a defaultable stock. The defaultable stock process proposed by Davis and Lischka (1999), Andersen and Buffum (2004), and Bloomberg (2009), etc., is given by

$$dS(t) = (r(t) + h(t))S(t_-)dt + \hat{\sigma}S(t_-)dW(t) - S(t_-)dU(t) \quad (3)$$

where $U(t)$ is an independent Poisson process with $dU(t) = 1$ with probability $h(t)dt$ and 0 otherwise, $h(t)$ is the hazard rate or the default intensity, $S(t_-)$ is the stock price immediately before any jump at time t . The expectation of $dU(t)$ is $E(dU(t)|\mathcal{F}_t) = h(t)dt$.

The expectation of equation (3) is given by

$$E(dS(t)|\mathcal{F}_t) = (r(t) + h(t))S(t)dt - S(t)h(t)dt = r(t)S(t)dt \quad (4)$$

The jump-diffusion model was first proposed in the context of market risk, which naturally exhibits high skewness and leptokurtosis levels and captures the so-called implied volatility smile or skew effects. Ederington and Lee (1993) find that the markets tend to have overreaction and underreaction to the outside news. The jump part of the model can be interpreted as the market response to outside news. If there is not any outside news, the asset price changes according to a geometric Brownian motion. Since the market price of risk and risk preferences are irrelevant to asset pricing within the market risk context, the expected rate of return to the stockholders is equal to the risk-free rate under a risk-neutral measure.

The world of credit modeling is divided into two main approaches: structural models and reduced-form (or intensity) models. The structural models regard default as an endogenous event, focusing on the capital structure of a firm. The reduced-form models do not explain the event of default endogenously, but instead characterize it exogenously as a jump process. In general, structural models are based on the information set available to the firm's management, such as the firm's assets and liabilities; while reduced-form models are based on the information set available to the market, such as the firm's bond prices or credit default swap (CDS) premia. Many practitioners in the credit trading arena have tended to gravitate toward the reduced-form models given their mathematical tractability. The reduced-form models can be made consistent with the risk-neutral probabilities of default backed out from corporate bond prices or CDS spreads/premia.

In the reduced-form models, the stopping (or default) time τ of a firm is modeled as a Cox arrival process (also known as a doubly stochastic Poisson process) whose first jump occurs at default and is defined as,

$$\tau = \inf \left\{ t : \int_0^t h(s, \Phi_s) ds \geq \Delta \right\} \quad (5)$$

where $h(t)$ or $h(t, \Phi_t)$ denotes the stochastic hazard rate or arrival intensity dependent on an exogenous common state Φ_t , and Δ is a unit exponential random variable independent of Φ_t .

It is well-known that the survival probability from time t to s in this framework is defined by

$$p(t, s) := P(\tau > s \mid \tau > t, Z) = \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (6)$$

The default probability for the period (t, s) in this framework is given by

$$q(t, s) := P(\tau \leq s \mid \tau > t, Z) = 1 - p(t, s) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (7)$$

We consider a defaultable asset that pays nothing between dates t and T . Let $V(t)$ and $V(T)$ denote its values at t and T , respectively. Risky valuation can be generally classified into two categories: the *default time approach* (DTA) and the *default probability (intensity) approach* (DPA).

The DTA involves the default time explicitly. If there has been no default before time T (i.e., $\tau > T$), the value of the asset at T is $V(T)$. If a default happens before T (i.e., $t < \tau \leq T$), a recovery payoff is made at the default time τ as a fraction of the market value² given by $\phi V(\tau)$ where ϕ is the default recovery rate and $V(\tau)$ is the market value at default. Under a risk-neutral measure, the value of this defaultable asset is the discounted expectation of all the payoffs and is given by

$$V(t) = E\left[\left(D(t, T)V(T)1_{\tau > T} + D(t, \tau)\phi V(\tau)1_{\tau \leq T}\right) \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (8)$$

² Here we use the recovery of market value (RMV) assumption.

where 1_Y is an indicator function that is equal to one if Y is true and zero otherwise, and $D(t, \tau)$ denotes the stochastic risk-free discount factor at t for the maturity τ given by

$$D(t, \tau) = \exp\left[-\int_t^\tau r(u)du\right] \quad (9)$$

The DPA relies on the probability distribution of the default time rather than the default time itself. We divide the time period (t, T) into n very small time intervals (Δt) and assume that a default may occur only at the end of each very small period. In our derivation, we use the approximation $\exp(y) \approx 1 + y$ for very small y . The survival and default probabilities for the period $(t, t + \Delta t)$ are given by

$$\hat{p}(t) := p(t, t + \Delta t) = \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx 1 - h(t)\Delta t \quad (10)$$

$$\hat{q}(t) := q(t, t + \Delta t) = 1 - \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx h(t)\Delta t \quad (11)$$

The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. For the one-period $(t, t + \Delta t)$ economy, at time $t + \Delta t$ the asset either defaults with the default probability $q(t, t + \Delta t)$ or survives with the survival probability $p(t, t + \Delta t)$. The survival payoff is equal to the market value $V(t + \Delta t)$ and the default payoff is a fraction of the market value: $\varphi(t + \Delta t)V(t + \Delta t)$. Under a risk-neutral measure, the value of the asset at t is the expectation of all the payoffs discounted at the risk-free rate and is given by

$$V(t) = E\left\{\exp(-r(t)\Delta t) [\hat{p}(t) + \varphi(t)\hat{q}(t)]V(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \approx E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)V(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (12)$$

where $y(t) = r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi(t)) = r(t) + c(t)$ denotes the risky rate and $c(t) = h(t)(1 - \varphi(t))$ is called the (short) credit spread.

Similarly, we have

$$V(t + \Delta t) = E\left\{\exp(-y(t + \Delta t)\Delta t)V(t + 2\Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right\} \quad (13)$$

Note that $\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)$ is $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable. By definition, an $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable random variable is a random variable whose value is known at time $t + \Delta t$. Based on the *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
V(t) &= E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)V(t+\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\
&= E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)E\left[\exp(-y(t+\Delta t)\Delta t)V(t+2\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right]|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\
&= E\left\{\exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^1 y(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t\right)V(t+2\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

By recursively deriving from t forward over T and taking the limit as Δt approaches zero, the risky value of the asset can be expressed as

$$V(t) = E\left\{\exp\left[-\int_t^T y(u)du\right]V(T)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \tag{15}$$

The derivation of equation (15) takes into account all credit characteristics: possibility of a jump to default and recovery rate. It tells us that a defaultable asset under the risk-neutral measure grows at a *risky rate*. The risky rate is equal to a risk-free interest rate plus a credit spread. If the asset is a bond, the equation is the same as Equation (10) in Duffie and Singleton (1999), which is the market model for pricing risky bonds. The market bond model says that the value of a risky bond is obtained by discounting the promised payoff using the risk-free interest rate plus the credit spread³.

In asset pricing theory, the fundamental no-arbitrage theorems do not require expected returns to be equal to the risk free rate, but only that prices are martingales after discounting under the numeraire. For risk-free valuation, people commonly use a risk-free bond as the numeraire, whereas for risky valuation, they should choose an associated risky numeraire to reflect credit risk. The expected return is that of the numeraire.

According to equation (15), we propose a risky model that embeds the probability of the default jump rather than the default jump itself into the price dynamics of an asset. The stochastic differential equation (SDE) of a defaultable stock is defined as

$$dS(t) = (r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi_s(t)))S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) = y(t)S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) \tag{16}$$

where φ_s is the recovery rate of the stock and $y(t) = r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi_s(t))$ is the risky rate.

³ There is a liquidity component in the bond spread. This paper, however, focuses on credit risk only.

Equation (16) is the direct derivation of equation (15). The formula allows different assumptions concerning recovery on default. In particular, $\varphi_s = 0$ represents the situation where the stock price jumps to 0, and $\varphi_s = 1$ corresponds to the risk-free case. The expectation of equations (16) is

$$E(dS(t)|\mathcal{F}_t) = (r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi_s(t)))S(t)dt \quad (17)$$

Equation (17) says that the expected return of a stock subject to credit risk is equal to a risky rate rather than the risk-free rate. The risky rate reflects the compensation investors receive for bearing credit risk.

3. PDE Algorithm

The defaultable stock price process is given by

$$dS(t) = (r(t) - q(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi_s(t)))S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) = \mu(t)S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) \quad (18)$$

where $q(t)$ is the dividend and $\mu(t) = r(t) - q(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi_s(t))$.

Suppose that $G(S, t)$ is some function of S and t . Applying Ito Lemma, we have

$$dG = \left(\mu S \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} + \frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial S^2} \right) dt + \sigma S \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} dW \quad (19)$$

Since the Wiener process underlying S and G are the same, we can construct the following portfolio so that the Wiener process can be eliminated.

$$X = G - S \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} \quad (20)$$

Therefore, we have

$$dX = dG - \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} dS = \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial S^2} \right) dt \quad (21)$$

In contrast to all previous studies, we believe that the defaultable equity should grow at the risky rate of the equity including dividends, whereas the equity part of the convertible bond should earn the risky rate of the equity excluding dividends, i.e.,

$$(r + h(1 - \varphi_s))Gdt - (r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s))\frac{\partial G}{\partial S}Sdt = dX = \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial S^2} \right)dt \quad (22)$$

So that the PDE of the equity component is given by

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial S^2} + (r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s))S \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} - (r + h(1 - \varphi_s))G = 0 \quad (23)$$

Similarly applying Ito Lemma to the bond part of the convertible $B(S, t)$, we obtain

$$dB = \left(\mu S \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} + \frac{\partial B}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial S^2} \right)dt + \sigma S \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} dW \quad (24)$$

Let us construct a portfolio so that we can eliminate the Wiener process as follows

$$Y = B - S \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} \quad (25)$$

Thus, we have

$$dY = dB - \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} dS = \left(\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial S^2} \right)dt \quad (26)$$

The defaultable equity should grow at the risky rate of the equity including dividends, while the bond part of the convertible bond grows at the risky rate of the bond. Consequently, we have

$$(r + h(1 - \varphi_b))Bdt - (r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s))\frac{\partial B}{\partial S}Sdt = dY = \left(\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial S^2} \right)dt \quad (27)$$

where φ_b is the recovery rate of the bond.

The PDE of the bond component is

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial S^2} + (r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s))S \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} - (r + h(1 - \varphi_b))B = 0 \quad (28)$$

Equations (23) and (28) are coupled through appropriate final and boundary conditions reflecting the terms and conditions of each individual convertible and need to be solved simultaneously. Convertible bonds often incorporate various additional features, such as call and put provisions.

The final conditions at maturity T can be generalized as

$$G_T = \begin{cases} \eta S_T, & \text{if } \eta S_T > \min [P_c, \max (P_p, N + C)] \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

$$B_T = \begin{cases} \min [P_c, \max (P_p, N + C)] & \text{if } \eta S_T \leq \min [P_c, \max (P_p, N + C)] \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

where N denotes the bond principal, C denotes the coupon, P_c denotes the call price, P_p denotes the put price and η denotes the conversion ratio. The final conditions tell us that the convertible bond at the maturity is either a debt or an equity.

The upside constraints at time $t \in [0, T]$ are

$$\begin{cases} G_t = \eta S_t, B_t = 0 & \text{if } \eta S_t > \min[P_c, \max(P_p, \tilde{L}_t)] \\ G_t = 0, B_t = P_p & \text{else if } \tilde{L}_t \leq P_p \\ G_t = 0, B_t = P_c & \text{else if } \tilde{L}_t \geq P_c \\ G_t = \tilde{G}_t, B_t = \tilde{B}_t & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

where $\tilde{L}_t = \tilde{B}_t + \tilde{G}_t$ is the continuation value of the convertible bond, \tilde{B}_t is the continuation value of the bond component and \tilde{G}_t is the continuation value of the equity component. Equation (31) says that the convertible is either in the continuation region or one of the three constraints (called, put or converted). One can use finite difference methods to solve the PDEs (23) and (28) for the price of a convertible bond.

4. Empirical results

We only consider the convertibles outstanding during the period and with sufficient pricing information. As a result, we obtain a final sample of 164 convertible bonds and a total of $164 \times 522 = 85,608$ observations. None of the convertibles in this sample actually defaulted during the time window.

Convertible bond prices observed in the market will be compared with theoretical prices under different volatility assumptions. The sample is segmented into two sets according to maturities: a short-maturity class (0 ~ 8 years) and a long-maturity class (> 8 years). We first select a convertible bond from each group: a 7-year (or 5-year outstanding) contract and a 20-year (or 17-year outstanding) contract shown in Table 1.

Figure 1. Maturity distribution of convertible bonds

This histogram splits the total number of convertible bonds of the sample into different classes according to the maturity of each convertible bond. The x-axis represents maturities in years and the y-axis represents

the number of convertibles in each class. The n maturity class covers contracts with maturities ranging from $n-1$ years to n years.

Table 1. Convertible bond examples

We hide the issuer names according to the security policy of the investment bank, but everything else is authentic. In the market, either a conversion price or a conversion ratio is given for a convertible bond, where conversion ratio = (face value of the convertible bond) / (conversion price).

Convertible bond	Case 1 (a 7-year convertible)	Case 2 (a 20-year convertible)
Issuer	X company	Y company
Principal of bond	100	100
Annual coupon rate	2.625	5.5
Payment frequency	Semiannual	Semiannual
Issuing date	June 9, 2010	June 15, 2009
Maturity date	June 15, 2017	June 15, 2029
Conversion price	30.288	13.9387
Currency	USD	USD
Day count	30/360	30/360

Business day convention	Following	Following
Put price	-	100 at June 20, 2014

The middle part of the curve is constructed using Eurodollar futures that require convexity adjustments. The far end is derived using mid swap rates. The LIBOR-future-swap curve is presented in Table 2. We bootstrap the curve and get the continuously compounded zero rates.

Table 2: A list of instruments used to build a USD interest rate curve

This table displays the closing prices as of September 10, 2012. These instruments are used to construct an interest rate curve.

Instrument Name	Price
September 19, 2012 LIBOR	0.6049%
September 2012 Eurodollar 3 month	99.6125
December 2012 Eurodollar 3 month	99.6500
March 2013 Eurodollar 3 month	99.6500
June 2013 Eurodollar 3 month	99.6350
September 2013 Eurodollar 3 month	99.6200
December 2013 Eurodollar 3 month	99.5900
March 2014 Eurodollar 3 month	99.5650
2 year swap rate	0.3968%
3 year swap rate	0.4734%
4 year swap rate	0.6201%
5 year swap rate	0.8194%
6 year swap rate	1.0537%
7 year swap rate	1.2738%
8 year swap rate	1.4678%
9 year swap rate	1.6360%
10 year swap rate	1.7825%
12 year swap rate	2.0334%
15 year swap rate	2.2783%
20 year swap rate	2.4782%

25 year swap rate	2.5790%
30 year swap rate	2.6422%

Unlike other studies that use bond spreads for pricing (see Tsiveriotis and Fernandes (1998), Ammann *et al* (2003), Zabolotnyuk *et al* (2010), etc.), we perform risky valuation based on credit information extracted from CDS spreads. Given the recovery rates and the CDS premia, we can compute the hazard rates via a standard calibration process (J.P. Morgan, 2001).

Table 3. Equity and recovery information

This table displays the closing stock prices and dividend yields on September 10, 2012, as well as the recovery rates

	Company X	Company Y
Stock price	34.63	23.38
Dividend yield	2.552%	3.95%
Bond recovery rate	40%	36.14%
Equity recovery rate	2%	1%

Table 4. CDS premia

This table displays the closing CDS premia as of September 10, 2012.

Name	Company X	Company Y
6 month CDS spread	0.00324	0.01036
1 year CDS spread	0.00404	0.01168
2 year CDS spread	0.00612	0.01554
3 year CDS spread	0.00825	0.01924
4 year CDS spread	0.01027	0.02272
5 year CDS spread	0.01216	0.02586
7 year CDS spread	0.01388	0.02851
10 year CDS spread	0.01514	0.03003
15 year CDS spread	0.01544	0.03064

20 year CDS spread	0.01559	0.03101
--------------------	---------	---------

For the 17-year outstanding convertible bond (case 2 in Table 1), however, most liquid stock options have relatively short maturates (rarely more than 8 years). Therefore, some authors, such as Ammann *et al* (2003), Loncarski *et al* (2009), Zabolotnyuk *et al* (2010), have to make do with historical volatilities. Similarly, we calculate the historical volatility as the annualized standard deviation of the daily log returns of the last 2 years (from September 10, 2010 to September 10, 2012), and then value the convertible bond based on this real-world volatility. The result shown in Table 5 reports an underpricing of 1.07%. The test results demonstrate that the model prices are very close to the market prices, indicating that the model is quite accurate.

Table 5. Model prices vs. market prices

This table shows the differences between the model prices and the market prices of the convertible bonds under different volatility assumptions, where $\text{Difference} = (\text{Model price}) / (\text{Market observed price}) - 1$. The convertible bonds are defined in Table 1.

	Case 1 (a 7-year convertible)	Case 2 (a 20-year convertible)
Type of volatility	ATM implied Black-Scholes volatility	Annualized historical volatility
Value of volatility	31.87%	18.07%
Model price	134.32	171.58
Market observed price	134.88	169.77
Difference	-0.42%	1.07%

We repeat this exercise for all contracts on all observation dates. For any short-maturity convertible bond, we use the ATM implied Black-Scholes volatility for pricing, whereas for any long-maturity convertible bond, we perform valuation via the historical volatility. The results are presented in Tables 6.

Table 6. Underpricing statistics for different maturity classes

An observation corresponds to a price snapshot of a convertible bond at a certain valuation date. Underpricing is referred to as the model price minus the market price.

Maturity	Observations	Underpricing			
		Mean (%)	Std (%)	Max (%)	Min (%)
≤ 8 years	82998	-0.13	1.37	0.79	-1.08
> 8 years	2610	1.67	2.03	2.24	0.58

Next, our sample is partitioned into subsamples according to the moneyness of convertibles. The moneyness is measured by the ratio of the conversion value to the equivalent straight bond value or the investment value. The underpricing of each daily observation with respect to the degree of moneyness is shown in Table 7, where moneyness between 0 and 0.9 corresponds to out-of-the-money; moneyness between 0.9 and 1.1 represents around-the-money; and moneyness higher than 1.1 is related to in-the-money.

Table 7. Underpricing statistics for different moneyness classes

The moneyness is measured by dividing the conversion value through the associated straight bond value. An observation corresponds to a snapshot of the market used to price a convertible bond at a certain valuation date.

Moneyness	Observations	Underpricing	
		Mean (%)	Std (%)
< 0.5	5794	0.72	2.23
0.5 – 0.7	10595	-0.87	2.37
0.7 – 0.9	19850	0.51	1.64
0.9 – 1.1	14737	0.45	1.12
1.1 – 1.3	14379	-0.55	1.89
1.3 – 1.5	11631	-0.42	2.04
> 1.5	8622	-0.62	1.72

In a typical convertible bond arbitrage strategy, the arbitrageur entails purchasing a convertible bond and selling the underlying stock to create a delta neutral position. The number of shares sold short usually reflects a delta-neutral or market neutral ratio. It is well known that delta neutral hedging not only removes small directional risks but also is capable of making a profit on an explosive upside or downside breakout if the position's gamma is kept positive. As such, delta neutral hedging is great for uncertain stocks that are expected to make huge breakouts in either direction. Since convertible bonds are issued mainly by start-up or small companies, the chance of a large movement in either direction is very likely. Even for very small movements in the underlying stock price, profits can still be generated from the yield of the convertible bond and the interest rebate for the short position.

Figure 2. Delta vs spot price graph for a 7-year convertible bond

This graph shows how the delta of the 7-year convertible bond (described in Table 1) changes as the underlying stock price changes.

Figure 3. Variation in gamma vs. spot price for a 7-year convertible bond

This graph shows how the gamma of the 7-year convertible bond (described in Table 1) changes as the underlying stock price changes.

Figure 4. Delta plotted against changing spot price for a 20-year convertible bond

This graph shows how the delta of the 20-year convertible bond (described in Table 1) changes as the underlying stock price changes.

Figure 5. Gamma variation with spot price for a 20-year convertible bond

This graph shows how the gamma of the 20-year convertible bond (described in Table 1) changes as the underlying stock price changes.

5. Conclusion

Our study shows that risky asset pricing is quite different from risk-free asset pricing. In fact, the expectation of a defaultable asset actually grows at a risky rate rather than the risk-free rate. This conclusion is vital for risky valuation.

Empirically, we do not find evidence supporting a systematic underpricing hypothesis. We also find that convertible bonds have relatively large positive gammas, implying that convertible arbitrage can make a significant profit on a large upside or downside movement in the underlying stock price.

References

Ammann, M., Kind, A., and Wilde, C. (2003) Are convertible bonds underpriced? An analysis of the French market. *Journal of Banking & Finance* 27: 635-653.

Andersen, L. and Buffum, D. (2004) Calibration and implementation of convertible bond models. *Journal of Computational Finance* 7: 1-34.

Batta, G., Chacko, G. and Dharan, B. (2007) Valuation consequences of convertible debt issuance. Working paper.

Brennan, M. and Schwartz, E. (1980) Analyzing convertible bonds. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis* 15: 907-929.

Carr, P. and Linetsky, V. (2006) A jump to default extended CEV model: an application of Bessel processes. *Finance and Stochastics* 10: 303-330.

Choi, D., Getmansky, M. and Tookes, H. (2009) Convertible bond arbitrage, liquidity externalities, and stock prices. *Journal of Financial Economics* 91: 227-251.

Duffie, D., and Huang, M. (1996) Swap rates and credit quality. *Journal of Finance* 51: 921-949.

Ederington, L. and Lee, H. (1993) How markets process information: News releases and volatility. *Journal of Finance* 48: 1161-1191.

FinPricing, 2013, Pricing, <https://finpricing.com/lib/EqCppi.html>

Grimwood, R., and Hodges, S. (2002) The valuation of convertible bonds: a study of alternative pricing models. Working paper, Warwick University.

Hull, J. (2003) *Options, Futures and Other Derivatives (5th ed.)*. Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ.

Loncarski, I., Horst, J. and Veld C. (2009) The rise and demise of the convertible arbitrage strategy. *Financial Analysts Journal* 26: 35-50.

J. P. Morgan (1999) *The J. P. Morgan guide to credit derivatives*. Risk Publications.

Somanath, V.S. (2011) *International financial management*. I.K. International Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.

Xiao, T. (2013) An accurate solution for credit value adjustment (CVA) and wrong way risk. Working paper.